

METHODS OF IMPROVING SPEAKING SKILLS FOR KIDS

M. Orzikulova¹, G. Rustamova²

Abstract:

This piece of work gives useful data about the ways of improving speaking skills of children. The article informs some easy methods to make child to speak fluently in English. Moreover, it discusses the main problem that prevents young generation from expressing their ideas. It can explain some effective methods for both teachers and parents that can be very helpful to improve the speaking skills of the kid. There is information about funny games and strategies.

Key words: speaking skills, methods, language, education, children, stories, TV shows, movies, cartoons, communication, motivation, programs, shuttering, apraxia, selective mutism, tongue-tie, mystery box.

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Most parents want their children to be able to speak English fluently. English is the most common language and it's important for children to start developing language skills as soon as possible so they can communicate more easily. Spending time with your child from an early age is a key to teaching them language skills. This is especially important for children who are learning a new language, as they have a better chance of becoming good speakers. When children start speaking English from a young age, they tend to develop excellent speaking skills. Let's learn about a few ways in which you can improve your child's English-speaking skills.

Developing language skills is not difficult, but the only key to effectively grasping the gifts is to practice consistently. Daily practice can do wonders for your child's speaking skills. In this article, we have discussed some ways to help you develop the English-speaking skills of your child. One of the things that you can do is to inculcate a reading habit. This can only be done by buying your child books of his interests. It can be about their favorite fictional character, or a simple motivational storybook, with great stories and life lessons. If your child likes to be updated with the current affairs and news, make sure that you get him newspapers and magazines to read. Sit with your kid and make time for reading. Reading stories to your child can help them learn new words and improve their vocabulary. With each page filled with colorful pictures and simple language, your child will be building up their vocabulary skills. It's a great alternative to listening to audio stories, and even better if your child reads them to you himself! [1]

Decide what to watch. On the weekends, watching TV shows and movies is a terrific way to unwind. We turn to TV whenever we want to have fun. Kids who

¹ *Orzikulova Mavsuma Mamatkulovna, Teacher of Samarkand State Institute of Foreign languages*

² *Rustamova Gulshan Utkurovna, Teacher of Samarkand State Institute of Foreign languages*

watch age-appropriate English television can expand their vocabulary and learn new terms. Furthermore, children's English-speaking abilities can be enhanced by the shows' use of simple English sentences. Permit your kid to watch English-language cartoons. We can select to watch cartoons in English since we live in a period when technology such as DTH and HDTV allows us to alter the language on TV shows we wish to watch. Though some children may initially find this adjustment difficult, with time they will grow to like it and pick up some basic English. Encourage Your Child to converse in English at home. Children will talk to you more because they spend most of their time at home. You have enough time to begin teaching English. They are encouraged to respond in the same tongue as a result. Learning some fundamental English phrases and conversational skills at home will help you become more comfortable speaking the language in public. Encourage them at every turn. Your child may attempt to answer in short English sentences when you begin speaking to him in the language. At first, the toddler will make errors and keep making the same ones. You have an obligation to reprimand him without upsetting them. Encourage them to give it more and try speaking again. If you make this a routine, you can get your aim. Keep A Diary in English. Some Children often love to pen down things. They have their separate notebook to write things down about their day or friends. If your kid is among one of those, ask him to pen down his thoughts in English. This will improve the English-speaking skills of the child along with the writing skills. And with time, they will develop a habit of it, making fewer mistakes and more sense. Play some English music. I love how music can lift my spirits. Everyone is greatly affected by it, thus in order to relax, individuals choose to listen to their favorite music. Just as we requested that you select to watch TV shows in English, you ought to favor listening to English-language music. The tunes follow an easy-to-memorize repetitious structure. Songs are especially more quickly remembered by children. They will improve their vocabulary and learn how to pronounce particular words by listening to these tunes. Engage in English Conversation with Friends. As kids get older, they talk to their friends a great deal. Kids will benefit by speaking English with their peers when they are at school, taking tuition classes, or on the phone. The fact that children feel so at ease with their pals is a big benefit of speaking English with them. They are able to communicate fluently since they are not under any pressure to be evaluated for their blunders.

Your child's English-speaking abilities will eventually improve, and they will be able to converse in the language with ease. Play Word Games. An exciting and engaging method to develop the vocabulary of the child is to play word games. This will enhance the knowledge of the words, and with a daily routine of playing word games, your kid will search for new terms every day from different mediums. Sing Out Loud. Rhymes and poems are other interactive ways to develop language skills in the child. With repetitive word patterns, kids tend to memorize new words. When they recite the lyrics in front of friends and classmates, they gain confidence and improve pronunciation. Kids quickly pick up the language and learn it effectively. With the constant hearing of the same words, the kids eventually register the names in their minds and eventually develop English speaking skills.

As they learn their first language, they can also improve English speaking with consistent practice with the right tips and approach. Make sure to follow a rigorous pattern to teach effectively. It is essential to provide them a suitable environment to learn a new language. The process may appear time-consuming,

but every second spent on polishing the English-speaking skills will enhance your child's confidence in the language. [2] Speech impediment, or speech disorder, happens when your child can't speak or can't speak so people understand what they're saying. In some cases, a speech impediment is a sign of physical or developmental differences.

Left untreated, a speech impediment can make it difficult for children to learn to read and write. Children with speech impediments might also have trouble socializing. There are some speech impediments like tongue tie or cleft palate that may be treated with surgery. In most cases, however, speech therapy helps treat speech impediments.[3] That speech impediments always brings forward very big problems for your child that prevent speaking fluently in a given language. Mostly children would have a sense of shame when they have these kind of speech impediments.

Stuttering. This condition may indicate developmental delay, an inherited condition or a sign your child's brain isn't coordinating the functions that drive speech.

Articulation errors. This happens when children can't form speech sounds because they have trouble with placing their tongue in the right position. Lipping is an example of an articulation error.

Tongue-tie (ankyloglossia). That is considered as a physical condition that makes it hard for children to move their tongues.

Apraxia. This condition occurs when a child's brain can't coordinate the muscles that enable speech.

Dysarthria. This condition happens when children slur their words because of brain damage.

Selective mutism. This condition happens when children become so anxious about being in certain places and situations that they can't speak.[4]

There are several very engaging games that are really effective to improve kid's speaking skills. Funny pictures- Find unusual pictures and show them to a child and make him to try using observation skill and explain the image. Teacher also can give some words or phrases that should be used. It will definitely help your child to develop his or her fluency in foreign languages.

That or this / would you rather- Those games are not useful for not only critical thinking but also helpful for developing reasoning skills: inductive and deductive. These activities are so effective for teaching completeness and clarity.

Mystery box- Put any object into the box and call the kids one by one in order to describe those objects. But they should not use the names of the objects. They must say the definition and classification of object. It is a great way to develop gestures and expressions.

Start with it- teachers can also play with different prompts like stories or complete sentences like I would love to assist, I am really glad because, or others. This helps them to explore their creativity, imagination and completeness of their speech.

Disappearing Text- if you are a parent, just write some words on the blackboard then erase them. It is so fun how many words do they remember. You can catch pronunciation errors during the game. It is so helpful for kids to practice their English. One of the most vital aspects of speaking is confidence and getting rid of the stage fear. If parents make their children to do these activities at home, they will be more confident in front of their teacher than ever before. Educators must motivate every young pupil to participate, while parents

can take time to engage their children in these activities at home. Verbal communication could be a challenge for many, however with long term practice and right support, it becomes much easier when it can be made exiting for the child learn.[5]

To take all into consideration, both educators and parents should work equally in order to prevent the kids from different troubles and problems related to improving speech. Different types of funny games and effective methods help them to tackle the issue easily.

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